

Design and Fabrication of a Miniaturized Microstrip Antenna Loaded by DNG Metamaterial

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Abstract : In this paper the design, fabrication and testing of a miniaturized rectangular microstrip patch antenna loaded with DNG metamaterials is reported. The metamaterial is composed of two nested spiral strips and a single straight strip which are etched on two sides of a 5.7 mm×5.7 mm Rogers RT/duroid 5880 with 0.5 mm thickness and dielectric constant of 2.2. Two units of this structure as a double negative (DNG) medium in combination with air as a double positive (DPS) medium are used as substrate of the microstrip patch antenna. By placing these metamaterial structures under the patch, a sub-wavelength resonance occurs which leads to a smaller size patch antenna compared to the conventional antenna at that frequency. The total size of the proposed antenna is reduced 54.6%. The dimensions of the proposed patch antenna are significantly smaller than the wavelength of the operation frequency with respect to the conventional patch antenna. Simulation result and test result for the proposed patch antenna are given and compared.

Keywords : Antennas, Metamaterials, Microstrip Antennas, Miniaturization

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